

Climate Change, Gender and Media in Nigeria: Mainstreaming Gender in Climate Change Reporting

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Abstract

Climate change represents one of the most pressing global challenges, with far-reaching impacts across social, economic, and environmental systems. However, its effects are not evenly distributed, as existing inequalities shape differential vulnerabilities among populations. This paper interrogates the gendered dimensions of climate change, arguing that women and marginalised groups particularly in developing countries, experience disproportionate impacts due to entrenched socio-economic, cultural, and political disparities. Based on secondary data from the existing literature, the study highlights how climate change exacerbates challenges related to health, food security, water access, livelihoods, education, and exposure to violence, thereby reinforcing gender inequality. Anchored in framing theory, the paper analyses how media representations influence perception, agenda-setting, and policy prioritisation. It argues that the media serves as a powerful agent in raising awareness, amplifying marginalised voices, and promoting gender-sensitive narratives that can drive inclusive climate action. Through illustrative case studies from Nigerian print media, the paper demonstrates emerging efforts and best practices in mainstreaming gender into climate reporting, while also identifying gaps in representation and depth of coverage. The paper concludes that effective climate action requires the integration of gender perspectives into communication, policy, and practice.

Keywords

climate change; gender; mainstreaming; media and reporting

I. Introduction

The advent of climate change affects sectors of society. However, while climate change poses one form of risk or the other to everyone, it does not affect everyone equally. Climate change has a more significant impact on gender. The impact of climate change on gender, especially in developing countries, comes with greater vulnerabilities due to existing social, economic, and political inequalities. Many times, the connection between climate change and gender is a critical, yet, often overlooked aspect of environmental discourse. As climate change intensifies, its impacts disproportionately affect women and marginalised gender groups, particularly in vulnerable communities (Owens-Ibie & Aondover, 2025). Across the globe, women often face heightened risks due to socio-economic inequalities, cultural norms, and their roles in managing household resources like water and food. In many societies, women are primarily responsible for managing natural resources, such as water and food, hence the impact of climate change effects, like droughts or floods disproportionately affect their livelihoods.

Also, climate change aggravates health issues that disproportionately affect women, such as maternal health complications and increased exposure to vector-borne diseases, etc. According to UNWOMEN (2022), climate change crisis is not “gender neutral” as women and girls experience the greatest impacts of climate change, which amplifies existing gender inequalities and poses unique threats to their livelihoods, health, and safety. The impact of climate change on gender is therefore complex and multifaceted, highlighting the need for gender-sensitive approaches in climate policies and programmes (Guanah et al., 2026). Incorporating a gender-sensitive approaches in climate policies and programmes cannot however be achieved unless there are some actions to shape public discourse by the media.

The media therefore plays a crucial role in shaping public opinion and influencing policy decisions, particularly regarding issues like climate change and gender. In creating desired awareness and education for climate change and gender policy actions, the media serves as a primary source of information, educating the public about the causes and consequences of climate change and gender-related issues. By providing accurate and timely information, media outlets can also raise awareness and foster informed public discussions (Aondover et al., 2024).

The media’s roles in framing issues are also significant. How the media frames climate change and gender significantly influence public perception. For example, portraying climate change as an urgent crisis can muster public concern and action, while emphasising gender inequalities can highlight the need for inclusive solutions. The role of the media in highlighting and amplifying the voices of marginalised groups, including women affected by climate change help humanise the issues and drive empathy and understanding of policy makers. The media also facilitates discourse by framing climate change and gender as critical issues, thereby galvanising politicians and policy makers to address such issues within the jurisprudence of policy reforms and legislative administration, etc (Moropefoluwa et al., 2024). By shaping narratives, raising awareness, and providing a platform for diverse voices, the media is instrumental in influencing public opinion and guiding policy decisions related to climate change and gender (Aondover & Obasi, 2025).

The interplay of the dynamics of the media’s role in advancing gender issues in climate change issues is therefore crucial in creating a more equitable and effective strategy for climate adaptation and mitigation. This study of the context of Climate Change, Gender and Media in Nigeria is therefore imperative in mainstreaming gender in climate change reporting.

1.1 Objectives of the Study

1. To highlight the dynamism of the role of the media in engendering and raising awareness about the impact of climate change on gender.
2. To highlight the imperatives of mainstreaming gender in climate reporting
3. To identify and underscore best practices for gender-sensitive climate reporting in various media formats.

II. Review of Literature

2.1 Perspectives on Climate Change

According to World Meteorological Organization (WMO), "Climate change refers to changes in the climate system that are attributed to human activities and natural factors,

including variations in temperature, precipitation patterns, and more extreme weather events."

Meanwhile, the definition by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), refers to climate change as "a change in the state of the climate that can be identified (e.g., using statistical tests) by changes in the mean and/or the variability of its properties, and that persists for an extended period, typically decades or longer." The definition by Houghton (2009) is stated as thus: "Climate change is the shift in long-term weather patterns and averages across the globe, primarily caused by human activities, such as the burning of fossil fuels, deforestation, and industrial processes, leading to an increase in greenhouse gases in the atmosphere."

While Schneider (2001) noted that "Climate change refers to changes in the Earth's climate, particularly due to an increase in atmospheric greenhouse gas concentrations as a result of human activities, leading to global warming and associated impacts on weather patterns, sea levels, and ecosystems", Giddens, A. (2009) noted that "Climate change is a significant and lasting change in the statistical distribution of weather patterns over periods ranging from decades to millions of years, influenced largely by human-induced factors." One of the human induced contributing factors to climate change known as global warming, which is the long-term increase in Earth's average surface temperature due to human activities, particularly the emission of greenhouse gases (GHGs) such as carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), and nitrous oxide (N₂O). These gases trap heat in the atmosphere, leading to the greenhouse effect, which is a natural process that warms the planet.

2.2 Causative Factors of Climate Change

Climate change is driven by a variety of causative factors, both natural and anthropogenic (human-induced). The natural cause includes volcanic activity, solar radiation variability, ocean currents and earth's orbital change. The Anthropogenic (human-induced) factors include greenhouse gas emissions (Carbon Dioxide (CO₂) emitted from burning fossil fuels like coal, oil, and natural gas), deforestation, and industrial processes; (like Methane (CH₄) released during the production and transport of coal, oil, and natural gas, as well as from livestock and other agricultural practices) and combustion of fossil fuels and solid waste (Ademosu et al., 2026).

Other human-induced factors include deforestation (The clearing of forests for agriculture, urban development, and logging reduces the number of trees that can absorb CO₂, increasing atmospheric concentrations of greenhouse gases); Industrialisation (increased manufacturing and energy consumption); agricultural practices (intensive farming methods that contribute to emissions of methane and nitrous oxide); transportation (emission from fossil consumption by cars, trucks, airplanes, and ships are significant sources of greenhouse gas emissions, primarily due to fossil fuel consumption; and emission of methane from organic waste management (Aondover et al., 2024).

2.3 Impact of Climate Change on Women

The impact of climate change on women is significant and multifaceted, often exacerbating existing inequalities (Msughter & Idris, 2023). Here are some key areas where climate change affects women:

- a. Health risks: Climate change can lead to increased health risks for women, including higher rates of heat-related illnesses, respiratory issues from air pollution, and complications related to maternal health during extreme weather events.

In her research, Shrestha, R. (2020), discusses the interconnectedness of gender, climate change, and health, emphasising how climate-related changes such as extreme weather events, shifting disease patterns, and resource scarcity disproportionately affect women. The paper highlights specific vulnerabilities, such as the impact on reproductive health and increased risks of violence and exploitation during crises.

- b. Food insecurity: As women are primarily responsible for food production and nutrition in many households, effect of climate change on agricultural productivity through changing weather patterns, pests, and diseases, can lead to food insecurity and malnutrition.

Alston, M. (2013), while examining the intersection of gender, climate change, and food security, particularly in rural contexts, noted that climate change affects men and women differently. Alston postulated that women, who often manage households and food production, face heightened vulnerabilities due to social and economic inequalities. The paper highlights that women are primarily responsible for food production and preparation, making them critical to household food security. Hence, climate-related disruptions, such as droughts and floods, can severely impact their ability to provide nutritious food.

- c. Lack of access to water: Women and girls often bear the responsibility of fetching water for their families. Hence the advent of climate change can exacerbate water scarcity, making it more difficult and time-consuming for them to access clean water, impacting their health and educational opportunities.

Wong and Bhatia (2020) in their paper, explored the critical intersections between gender, climate change, and access to water resources: The authors highlight how climate change exacerbates water scarcity, which disproportionately affects women. According to them, women in many communities are primarily responsible for water collection, meaning they face increased burdens when access is limited. They also noted that limited access to clean water impacts not only health but also hygiene and sanitation. This is especially critical for women and girls, who may face health risks and diminished quality of life due to inadequate water supplies (Adewale et al., 2025).

- d. Economic impact: Climate change can disrupt livelihoods, particularly in sectors like agriculture, where many women work. Climate change can result in loss of income which invariably increase the poverty conditions of women.

Buvinić and O'Dell (2016) examined the economic impacts of climate change on women, emphasising the need for gender-sensitive approaches in climate action. The authors highlight that women are disproportionately affected by climate change, particularly in sectors like agriculture, where they often work. They noted that economic losses from climate-related events can significantly undermine women's livelihoods and economic stability. The article discusses how climate change can alter labour market conditions, affecting women's employment opportunities. They noted that displacement due to climate impacts can disrupt traditional roles, often resulting in women taking on additional caregiving responsibilities, which can limit their economic participation. They also noted that climate change-related health impacts, such as increased heat stress and the spread of diseases, can further reduce women's productivity. This results in both direct health costs and indirect economic costs due to lost income and reduced labor force participation.

- e. Exposure to violence and exploitation: When climate-related events, such as floods and droughts occur, women face heightened risks of violence and exploitation during displacement, as well as challenges in maintaining their cultural and familial ties.

Wambua (2021) in her paper explores the intersections of gender, climate change, and forced migration, particularly in the African context. The research highlights how women are particularly vulnerable to the impacts of climate change, including natural disasters and environmental degradation. She noted that women often face unique challenges during climate-induced migration, such as limited access to resources and support systems.

- f. Limits to access to education: Disruptions caused by climate change can impact girls' education. Increased household responsibilities, particularly during climate-induced crises, can lead to higher dropout rates for girls.
- g. Mental health: The stress and trauma associated with climate change, such as loss of livelihoods or homes, can significantly affect women's mental health, particularly in communities already facing socio-economic challenges.

Addressing the gender dimensions of climate change is essential for effective policy-making and sustainable development. By integrating gender perspectives into climate action, we can create more equitable and resilient communities.

III. Research Methods

3.1 The Role of the Media in Mainstreaming Gender into Climate Change Reporting

The crucial role that media plays in shaping policy cross-cuts various sectors, including environmental issues, health, social justice, and governance. In the light of the crucial role of the media in shaping public discourse and influencing policy, it has a responsibility to integrate gender perspectives into climate change reporting. Mainstreaming gender in climate change reporting is essential for ensuring that both the impacts of climate change and the responses to it are equitable and effective. The media plays a critical role in mainstreaming gender in climate change reporting, helping to highlight the distinct experiences and needs of different genders in the context of environmental issues (Obasi & Msughter, 2023; Okunade et al., 2025). Among others, the role of the media in mainstreaming gender into climate change reporting includes:

1. *Raising awareness and visibility of gender issues:* By covering the gendered impacts of climate change, media can raise awareness about how women, men, and marginalised groups are affected differently by environmental changes.
2. *Highlighting issues:* The media can bring attention to specific issues, framing them as important and urgent, which can influence public perception and push policymakers to address them. By choosing how to report on issues of gender and climate change reporting, the media can shape the narrative around women, invariably making the policymakers to understand the problems and potential solutions. Featuring stories of women who are affected by climate change or who are leading adaptation and mitigation efforts can provide a more nuanced understanding of the issues.
3. *Informing the public:* The media provides essential information that helps the public understand complex issues, which can lead to increased public engagement and advocacy. By covering diverse viewpoints and expert opinions, the media fosters public discourse that can lead to more informed policymaking about the diverse aspects of climate change and its impact on gender.
4. *Influencing public opinion and shaping attitudes:* Media coverage can shape public attitudes toward policy issues, influencing what the public sees as important and affecting the political climate. In driving gender concerns into climate change policies, media campaigns can mobilize public support for specific policies,

encouraging grassroots movements that can lead to political pressure on policymakers.

5. *Amplifying marginalised perspectives:* The media can elevate the voices of marginalised groups, ensuring that their needs and perspectives are considered in policy discussions about climate change issues. By facilitating discussions among various stakeholders, the media helps build consensus and encourage collaborative approaches to policy challenges as relating to climate change issues and gender concerns.
6. *Providing evidence:* The media often highlights research and data that can inform policymakers about the implications of specific policies and the effectiveness of different approaches. As it relates to mainstreaming gender into climate change issues, journalists can break down complex data and research findings into more digestible information for policymakers and the public.
7. *Providing a platform for advocacy:* Media can serve as a tool for empowerment, providing women with a platform to voice their experiences and advocate for their rights in the context of climate change.
8. *Promoting narratives that challenges stereotypes:* Media can challenge stereotypes and promote narratives that emphasize gender equality in climate action, encouraging broader societal recognition of women's roles in sustainability (Vitalis et al., 2023).
9. *Advocating for policy change:* Media can amplify the voices of activists and organizations working to promote gender equity in climate policies, influencing decision-makers and public opinion.
10. *Creating platforms for discussion:* Media can host debates, forums, and discussions that bring together various stakeholders to discuss gender and climate change, fostering collaboration and knowledge sharing. Media can also host webinars that bring together diverse stakeholders to discuss gender and climate issues, facilitating dialogue and knowledge sharing (Aondover et al., 2024).
11. *Encouraging community engagement:* Local media can engage communities in discussions about their specific challenges and solutions related to climate change, ensuring that diverse voices are heard.
12. *Innovative storytelling:* By employing various formats such as documentaries, podcasts, and social media campaigns the media can make gender and climate issues more relatable and impactful for different audiences.
Storytelling that centers on personal experiences can also humanize the issues, making the impacts of climate change on gender more tangible and urgent.
13. *Highlighting women leaders:* Media outlets can also publish profiles or feature stories on women who are leading climate initiatives, such as community organizers, scientists, and policymakers. For instance, profiles of women in agriculture who are implementing sustainable practices can showcase their contributions and challenges. Inviting women experts, activists, and scholars to share their insights on climate issues ensures that gender perspectives are included in the conversation. Panel discussions or op-eds featuring female voices can enhance representation.
14. *Reporting on gender-responsive policies:* Articles that analyse national and international climate policies through a gender lens can inform the public about the importance of integrating gender considerations in climate action.

By incorporating these approaches, the media can effectively mainstream gender in climate change reporting, contributing to a more inclusive and equitable discourse on environmental issues.

3.2 Framing Theory, Climate Change and Gender Reporting

Framing theory is a concept in communication and media studies that explores how, and the way information is presented influences perception and interpretation. Framing theory centers on how something that is presented to the audience (called “the frame”) influences the choices people make about how to process that information. Frames are abstractions that work to organise or structure message meaning (Vitalis et al., 2025). It is sometimes referred to as second-level agenda setting because of its close relation to Agenda-Setting Theory but expands the research by focusing on the essence of the issues at hand rather than on a particular topic. Framing is the way and manner information or message is presented which influence how the audience interprets it.

Anthropologist Gregory Bateson is credited with first positing the theory in 1972. He defined psychological frames as a “spatial and temporary bounding of set of interactive messages” (Bateson, 1972, p. 197) that operates as a form of metacommunication (Hallahan, 2008). On a general level, frames can be understood as having the propensity to categorise and connect large chunks of information and in doing so, reduce complexity in meaning. Hence, framing is essentially about selection and salience of information; as in the words of Entman (1993): “To frame is to select some aspect of a perceived reality and to make them more salient in a communicating text, in such a way as to promote a particular problem definition, casual interpretation moral evolution, and/or treatment recommendation for the item described” (p. 52).

According to Reese (2001), a frame can thus be defined as “organising principles that are socially shared and persistent over time, that work symbolically to meaningfully structure the social world” (p. 11). Frames are then essentially about providing meaning and something that everyone engages in when communicating. Frames are studied inductively and deductively, as dependent and independent variables. To increase the confusion, scholars have researched and located frames at different levels, including that of the audience, news organizations, news sources, news texts, as well as culture (Aondover et al., 2025).

Other perspectives on framing include that by Molly Anderson which emphasises the importance of gender analysis in climate policy, arguing that framing climate change through a gender lens helps illuminate the unique vulnerabilities and contributions of women; Karen O’Brien, which explores how social dimensions, including gender, shape vulnerability and adaptation strategies. She advocates for inclusive framing that recognizes diverse experiences; and Gina Ziervogel, which examines gendered frames in climate change adaptation in the Global South, emphasising the need for policies that address women's specific needs and roles (Aondover et al., 2025).

Meanwhile, while the postulation by O’Neill (2016) integrates feminist perspectives into climate communication, critiquing how traditional narratives often marginalise women's experiences, McKinnon (2019) analysed media representations of women in climate narratives, advocating for more empowering and less victim-centric framing. Furthermore, while Elena Van der Hoeven critiques international climate policies, highlighting how gender-sensitive approaches can be integrated into existing frameworks, Katherine Hayhoe, discusses the intersection of gender and climate perception, advocating for narratives that empower diverse voices in climate action.

All of the above, in different ways, illustrates how framing theory can provide valuable insights into the relationship between climate change and gender. Hence, by understanding how issues are framed in communication, scholars can better understand and advocate for inclusive narratives that address both the vulnerabilities and the agency of women in the context of climate change.

IV. Discussion

4.1 Case Studies and Best Practices in Media Reportage of Gender and Climate Change Issues

Whilst there is still much to be done by the media in mainstreaming gender into climate change reporting, there exists pockets of case studies and best practice in, media reportage of gender and climate change issues. Here are some randomly selected case studies from a cross section of Nigeria's print media that illustrate how the media is effectively mainstreaming gender into climate change reporting:

1. *The Guardian Nigeria*

#1: The article "The Female Face of Climate Change" by Caleb Adebayo from *The Guardian Nigeria* @ <https://guardian.ng/opinion/the-female-face-of-climate-change/> which was published on October 25, 2017 reveals that *women are 14 more times likely to die than men during a disaster*. The article further discusses the significant impact of climate change on women, emphasising their roles in communities, especially in agriculture and resource management. It highlights how women are often the primary caregivers and are disproportionately affected by environmental changes.

Key Points: Among others, the article highlights the following:

Women, particularly in rural areas, face greater risks from climate change due to existing socio-economic inequalities; women play crucial roles in climate adaptation strategies, leveraging traditional knowledge and practices to manage resources sustainably; the article calls for increased representation of women in climate policy discussions, recognising their contributions and addressing their specific needs; and the articles also showcases examples of women-led initiatives aimed at mitigating climate impacts and promoting resilience within their communities.

#2: The news article "Groups Boost Women Smallholder Farmers' Resilience to Climate Change" by Gbenga Salau of *The Guardian Nigeria* @ <https://guardian.ng/news/groups-boost-women-smallholder-farmers-resilience-to-climate-change> which was published on April 20, 2024 highlights initiatives aimed at strengthening the resilience of women smallholder farmers in the face of climate change.

Key Points: Among others, the article highlights the following:

Women smallholder farmers are particularly vulnerable to climate change impacts, such as unpredictable weather patterns and resource scarcity, which threaten their livelihoods; the news article discusses various organizations and community groups working to empower women farmers through training, resources, and support networks. These groups focus on sharing knowledge about sustainable farming practices and climate adaptation strategies; the reports notes that initiatives aimed at improving women's access to essential resources, such as credit, seeds, and technology, are highlighted.

These resources are crucial for enhancing their agricultural productivity and resilience; it noted that programmes that provide training in climate-smart agriculture and innovative farming techniques are essential for helping women adapt to changing environmental conditions; the news article also emphasises the importance of advocating for gender-sensitive policies that recognize and support the contributions of women in agriculture, ensuring their voices are included in decision-making processes; and the news report concluded by noting that by empowering women smallholder farmers, these efforts not only help women adapt to climate change but also contribute to food security and sustainable development in their communities, and invariably play a critical role in building resilience against climate impacts.

#3: The news article "Varsity Don Advocates Gender-Based Agricultural Policies" by NAN from *The Guardian Nigeria* @ <https://guardian.ng/news/varsity-don-advocates-gender-based-agricultural-policies/> which was published September 28, 2024 discusses the need for gender-sensitive approaches in agricultural policies to effectively address the challenges faced by women in farming. The article highlights the existing gender disparities in agriculture, where women often have limited access to resources, training, and decision-making opportunities compared to men.

Key Points: Among others, the report highlights the following:

Women play a significant role in agricultural production, yet their contributions are frequently undervalued and overlooked in policy frameworks; it emphasises the importance of developing agricultural policies that specifically consider the needs and challenges of women farmers, including access to credit, land, and technology; the news report notes that by empowering women in agriculture through tailored policies, the potential for increased food security and sustainable agricultural practices can be realised; and the news report article calls for stakeholders, including government and NGOs, to prioritise gender-based approaches in agricultural planning and implementation.

2. *Punch Nigeria*

#1: The news article "NGO Laments Negative Effect of Climate Change Over North Girls" by Chima Azubuike from *Punch Nigeria* @ <https://punchng.com/ngo-laments-negative-effect-of-climate-change-over-north-girls> discusses the impact of climate change on young girls in Northern Nigeria, highlighting how environmental challenges exacerbate existing socio-economic issues.

Key Points: Among others, the article highlights the following:

The news article emphasises that climate change significantly affects girls, particularly in the North, where environmental degradation and extreme weather events can lead to displacement, food insecurity, and health challenges; climate-related challenges, such as droughts and flooding, disrupt girls' education by forcing them to drop out of school to support their families or due to increased domestic responsibilities during crises; the report on the NGO points out that climate change contributes to health risks for girls, including malnutrition and increased susceptibility to diseases, as changing environmental conditions affect food availability and safety; it noted that with traditional livelihoods threatened, families may push girls into early marriages as a coping mechanism, limiting their opportunities and perpetuating cycles of poverty; the news article advocates for targeted interventions to address the specific needs of girls in climate adaptation strategies.

It emphasises the importance of education, healthcare access, and community support to empower these young women; and the report underscores the need for comprehensive strategies that consider the unique vulnerabilities of girls in the context of climate change, advocating for greater attention and resources to support their well-being and future prospects.

#2: The news article "Stakeholders Seek Enhanced Women Participation in Agriculture" By Daniel Adaji from *Punch Nigeria* @ <https://punchng.com/stakeholders-see-enhanced-women-participation-in-agriculture> which was published October 9, 2024 discusses the crucial need for increased participation of women in agriculture to address food security and climate change challenges.

Key Points: Among others, the article highlights the following:

The news article emphasises that women play a vital role in agricultural production in Nigeria, contributing significantly to food security and rural economies. Despite this, their contributions are often undervalued; it highlights various barriers that women face, including limited access to land, finance, training, and decision-making opportunities. These challenges hinder their ability to maximise their potential in agriculture; it noted that stakeholders are advocating for policy reforms that promote gender equality in agricultural practices.

This includes creating supportive environments that empower women farmers through better access to resources and opportunities; the news report discusses the importance of capacity-building programs that provide women with training in modern agricultural techniques, financial literacy, and leadership skills, enabling them to contribute more effectively; it stresses the need for collaboration among government, NGOs, and the private sector to develop initiatives that enhance women's roles in agriculture and ensure their voices are heard in policy discussions; and the news item concluded that by enhancing women's participation in agriculture, the potential for improved food security and resilience against climate change can be achieved. The news article calls for concerted efforts to break down barriers and promote gender-inclusive agricultural policies.

3. Vanguard

#1: The news article "Fish Farmers Groan as Climate Change, Inflation, Others Impede Sustainability" by Ebunoluwa Sessou from *Vanguard Nigeria* @ <https://www.vanguardngr.com/2023/10/fish-farmers-groan-as-climate-change-inflation-others-impede-sustainability/> which was published October 28, 2023, addresses the challenges faced by fish farmers, highlighting how climate change and economic pressures threaten the sustainability of aquaculture.

Key Points: Among others, the article highlights the following:

Fish farmers are experiencing the adverse effects of climate change, including rising water temperatures and altered aquatic ecosystems, which affect fish health and yield; rising costs of feed, equipment, and maintenance due to inflation are straining the financial viability of fish farming operations. Farmers express concerns about their ability to sustain production levels; issues like pollution and habitat destruction are compounded by climate change, leading to lower fish populations and reduced biodiversity, which further threatens the livelihoods of fish farmers; the news article discusses the need for innovative practices and technologies to enhance resilience among fish farmers. This includes better management of resources and sustainable practices that can mitigate the impacts of climate change; the news report noted that farmers are calling for greater support from government and NGOs in terms of funding, training, and access to resources that would help them adapt to the changing climate and economic conditions; and the article highlights the interconnectedness of climate change and economic factors in the fish farming industry, stressing the need for comprehensive solutions to ensure the sustainability of this critical food source.

4.2 Strategies for Mainstreaming Gender in Climate Change Reporting

- a. **Training and Capacity Building:** Provide training for journalists on gender issues and climate change to enhance their understanding and reporting skills.
- b. **Gender-Responsive Frameworks:** Encourage media organizations to adopt frameworks that prioritize gender analysis in climate reporting.
- c. **Collaborations and Partnerships:** Foster partnerships between media, NGOs, and gender experts to create comprehensive and nuanced climate narratives.

- d. **Use of Diverse Media Platforms:** Leverage various media formats—print, digital, and social media to reach diverse audiences and promote gender-inclusive messages.
- e. **Monitoring and Evaluation:** Establish mechanisms to assess the representation of gender in climate change reporting and identify gaps and areas for improvement.

V. Conclusion

Mainstreaming gender into climate change reporting is essential for creating equitable and effective responses to the climate crisis. By leveraging the power of media, we can ensure that diverse voices are heard and that solutions are inclusive, fostering a more just and sustainable future. This concept note serves as a call to action for media professionals, policymakers, and stakeholders to work together in this crucial endeavour.

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